

Expressing Negation During the Multiword Stage of Language Development¹

Meryem ÇALIŞKAN² 0000-0002-3127-6494

<p>ARTICLE HISTORY</p> <p>Received 11 Mar 2026 Accepted 05 Jun 2026</p> <p>KEYWORDS</p> <p>negation acquisition; child language acquisition; early language development; overgeneralization</p>	<p>ABSTRACT</p> <p>The acquisition of negation holds significant importance in early language development, shaping children's linguistic and cognitive development. This study explores the milestones regarding the acquisition of negation during the early stages of language development. By examining relevant research from linguistic studies and child language acquisition literature, the progression from single negative words to more complicated multiword expressions was clarified. The study uses purposively selected CHILDES and TalkBank data from children aged 2;0–3;6. The study highlights common errors and overgeneralization tendencies that children encounter as they master negation structures. The findings also emphasise the role of systematic error patterns in revealing children's developing grammatical knowledge during this stage. Ultimately, this research aims to contribute to the understanding of language acquisition processes and their implications for early language development.</p>
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Introduction

Language acquisition is a complex and dynamic process that goes through significant developmental stages during early childhood. One important aspect of language development is the acquisition and expression of negation, which plays a crucial role in conveying meaning and expressing negated structures and sentences. Previous research has mainly investigated the acquisition of negation in children, focusing on the early single-word stage (e.g., Brown, 1973; Choi, 1988). However, the transition to the multiword stage shows an important period when children expand their linguistic repertoire and begin constructing more complex and syntactically varied utterances. Understanding how negation is expressed during this stage is essential for gaining a comprehensive understanding of language development.

One of the earliest systematic investigations of negation in child language was conducted by Bellugi (1967), who identified developmental stages in children's use of negative constructions in English. Bellugi demonstrated that children initially express negation through external negative markers such as *no* placed before an utterance (e.g., *no eat cookie*). As their grammatical knowledge develops, children begin to incorporate negation within the sentence structure and eventually acquire adult-like forms involving auxiliary verbs and correct syntactic placement. This developmental sequence suggests that children gradually internalise the grammatical rules governing negation as their linguistic competence increases.

Based on the previous discussion regarding the development of negation in the multi-word stage of children, three research questions were formulated:

1. How do children in the multiword stage express negation in their language production?
2. What are the common syntactic structures or word combinations used by children in the multiword stage to convey negation?

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² Lect., Adana Alparslan Türkeş Science and Technology University, School of Foreign Languages, mcaliskan@atu.edu.tr.

3. What types of errors do children produce when expressing negation during the multiword stage?

The first research question in this study intends to explore how children in the multiword stage express negation in their language production. By investigating the different strategies and forms employed by children, we can explain the variations in their use of negation during this stage. This analysis contributes to our understanding of how negation is acquired and expressed as children progress in their language acquisition.

The second research question seeks to explore the common syntactic structures or word combinations utilised by children in the multiword stage to convey negation. By investigating the specific syntactic patterns and word combinations used by children, we can develop a deeper understanding of the emerging grammatical structures and syntactic rules shaping their negation expressions. This exploration enlightens the syntactic development and strategies employed by children during the multiword stage.

The third research question focuses on the types of errors children produce while using negation during the multiword stage. By identifying patterns such as overgeneralization, incorrect placement, and misuse of auxiliary verbs, this study aims to provide insights into the developmental challenges children encounter. Examining these errors contributes to a deeper understanding of how children gradually refine their grammatical competence and move toward target-like negation structures.

With the intention of addressing these research questions, this study draws on the literature on language acquisition, specifically focusing on the multiword stage of negation development.

Literature Review

The acquisition of negation in early language development is an essential aspect of linguistic growth, as it plays a substantial role in shaping children's communicative abilities. Research in the field of language acquisition has highlighted the significance of negation as a necessary grammatical and semantic feature in several languages. During the early stages of language development, children gradually learn to express negation using a wide range of strategies, starting from single negative words like "no" and "not" and improving to more complex multiword expressions involving auxiliary verbs (Bloom, 1990).

From another perspective, Bloom (1970) emphasised the semantic functions of negation in early child language. Her research showed that children use negative forms to express a variety of meanings, including rejection, denial, nonexistence, and prohibition. Bloom argued that the emergence of negation reflects both cognitive development and communicative needs, as children begin to express disagreement, refusal, and absence through linguistic means. These findings highlight the close relationship between conceptual development and the acquisition of grammatical structures.

Further insights into the development of negation were provided by Brown (1973) in his influential longitudinal study of early language development. Brown identified stages of grammatical development in children and observed that negative constructions evolve alongside other syntactic structures. According to Brown, children initially rely on simple negative markers but gradually acquire more complex constructions involving auxiliaries such as *do* and *be*. This progression reflects the broader development of grammatical competence during early childhood.

During the early stages of language development, children begin by using single negative words, such as "no" or "not," to convey negation in meaning (Brown, 1973). However, as children move into the multiword stage, they demonstrate a shift in their use of negation,

involving syntactic structures and combining multiple words to express negation more effectively (Crain & Thornton, 1998).

The acquisition of negation has been widely recognised as a cognitively and linguistically demanding aspect of early language development. Recent research suggests that understanding and processing negation involves complex mapping between linguistic form and conceptual meaning, which can pose difficulties for young learners (Gomes et al., 2023). From a psycholinguistic perspective, children must not only learn the lexical forms of negation but also integrate them into appropriate syntactic and semantic structures. Dudschig et al. (2021) further emphasise that the processing of negation is closely tied to broader mechanisms of language comprehension and polarity interpretation, highlighting that even seemingly simple negative constructions require advanced cognitive operations. These findings suggest that the acquisition of negation cannot be separated from general developmental changes in cognitive processing and language comprehension abilities.

Choi (2000) conducted longitudinal research analysing spontaneous language samples of children in the multiword stage. The findings indicated that children employ a variety of strategies to express negation, including the use of negative words (e.g., "no," "not") together with auxiliary verbs (e.g., "don't," "can't"). It is supported in this study that the combination of words allows children to convey negation more accurately and similar to the adult-like expressions observed in the language of parents, caregivers and the surrounding linguistic source.

Investigation by Abdulkarim et al. (1997) focused on the emergence of more complex syntactic features in the multiword stage of negation acquisition. Their findings showed that children start incorporating negation with auxiliary verbs (e.g., "don't," "can't") and engage in subject-verb combinations (e.g., "can't I go?") to express negation more effectively. This syntactic improvement demonstrates the progression of the syntactic abilities of children as they develop more sophisticated means of negation expression.

From a developmental standpoint, children's use of negation evolves in systematic stages, particularly during the transition into multiword speech. Early usage-based research shows that children initially rely on single-word negatives before gradually expanding into multiword constructions that reflect more adult-like syntactic patterns (Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2007). This progression is not uniform across languages; instead, cross-linguistic evidence indicates that the trajectory of negation acquisition is influenced by both universal developmental constraints and language-specific input patterns (Çabuk-Ballı et al., 2025). During the multiword stage, children often exhibit overgeneralization and non-target-like forms, which are considered important indicators of emerging grammatical knowledge. These systematic error patterns provide valuable insight into how children construct and refine their understanding of negation within developing grammatical systems.

Ultimately, these studies highlight the shift in negation expression during the multiword stage of language development. Children move from using single negative words to employing multiword expressions, integrating negative words with auxiliary verbs and showing syntactic flexibility in word order and subject-verb combinations. While the mentioned studies provide rewarding insights into negation acquisition in the multiword stage, further investigation is required to take the individual differences into account, to explore pragmatic aspects of negation, and to examine the cognitive elements in the development of negation during this stage.

Methodology

This section outlines the methodological framework adopted in the present study, which investigates how children in the multiword stage utilise negation during English language development. The study employs a qualitative document analysis approach by examining

previously collected child language data and relevant scholarly literature. Such an approach allows the researcher to explore patterns of negation use and developmental tendencies without conducting primary data collection.

Qualitative document analysis has been widely used in language acquisition research, particularly when researchers aim to examine naturally occurring language data collected in established corpora. Child language databases provide valuable longitudinal and cross-sectional records of children's spontaneous speech, allowing researchers to observe developmental patterns across different stages of language acquisition. Such data offer authentic examples of how children produce language in natural contexts, which helps researchers identify recurring linguistic structures and developmental tendencies in early speech production.

The research is grounded in the field of child language acquisition and focuses on identifying developmental patterns in children's use of negation. By analysing existing language corpora and peer-reviewed studies, the study aims to trace how children move from simple negative expressions to more complex multiword negation structures. This design enables the researcher to investigate linguistic forms, developmental sequences, and common patterns of error in children's early negation use.

Child language corpora provide an important resource for examining developmental patterns in naturalistic speech. One of the most widely used databases in this field is the CHILDES (Child Language Data Exchange System), which offers a large collection of transcribed interactions between children and their caregivers across different languages and developmental stages. The availability of such corpora allows researchers to analyse authentic language use and track linguistic development over time. As noted by MacWhinney (2000), corpus-based resources like CHILDES enable systematic investigation of children's speech while supporting reproducibility and comparative analysis across studies.

Corpus-based approaches are especially useful in studies of early language development because they allow researchers to analyse real-life language use rather than elicited responses in controlled experimental settings. By examining recorded child-caregiver interactions and previously documented linguistic data, researchers can gain insight into how children naturally acquire grammatical structures over time. This approach also enables the identification of frequent patterns, variations, and errors in children's speech, which are important indicators of the developmental processes underlying language acquisition.

The methodological approach is descriptive and analytical in nature. It emphasises identifying linguistic patterns within authentic child language data and interpreting these patterns in light of established theories of language acquisition. Special attention is given to the forms of negation used by children, the structural complexity of their utterances, and the types of errors observed during the developmental process.

Overall, the methodology is designed to provide a systematic examination of negation development in early language acquisition. By integrating corpus-based observations with insights from previous research, the study aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of how children develop the ability to express negation during the multiword stage.

Data Collection Instruments and Procedure

The data for this study were collected from multiple sources, including databases and academic journals. The primary sources of data were TalkBank and CHILDES, which are widely recognised repositories of conversational data used in research on language acquisition (MacWhinney, 2000). These databases contain extensive collections of transcripts and audio recordings of children's language development. The English section of the CHILDES database, in particular, was explored to access relevant corpora and transcripts.

In order to enhance methodological transparency, the data selection followed a purposive sampling strategy rather than relying on a fixed dataset. The analysis focused on a representative subset of transcripts drawn from the CHILDES and TalkBank corpora that included children in the multiword stage of language development. The selected data primarily involved children approximately between the ages of 2;0 and 3;6, a developmental period commonly associated with the emergence of multiword utterances and increasing syntactic complexity. Instead of limiting the analysis to a predetermined number of participants or transcripts, the study aimed to capture a range of naturally occurring negation patterns across different speakers and contexts. Transcripts were selected based on the presence of clear instances of negation use, ensuring that the dataset was sufficiently rich to illustrate both structural patterns and common error types in children's language production.

To access the TalkBank and CHILDES databases, permissions and guidelines for data access were followed, ensuring compliance with the terms of use and ethical considerations. The data retrieved from these databases consisted of transcripts and recordings of children's language production during the multiword stage, specifically focusing on instances of negation expression.

In order to ensure the relevance of the data to the aims of the study, the analysis focused specifically on transcripts representing children in the multiword stage of language development. The multiword stage is typically characterised by the production of two- or three-word combinations that reflect the emergence of basic grammatical relations. Therefore, the selected corpus data included utterances produced by children who were beginning to combine words into short phrases or sentences. This selection criterion allowed the study to focus on the developmental stage in which negation structures start to become more syntactically organised.

In addition to database sources, academic journals were consulted to supplement the dataset. The Education Resources Information Centre (ERIC), a comprehensive digital library of education research, was particularly valuable for accessing relevant studies and articles on negation acquisition in early language development. The articles retrieved from ERIC provided additional insights and perspectives on the topic, contributing to the breadth and depth of the study.

During the analysis process, particular attention was given to identifying instances in which children used negative markers such as *no*, *not*, *don't*, *can't*, and other forms expressing negation. These utterances were examined in order to observe patterns in their structural use, placement within sentences, and level of grammatical complexity. By categorising these examples and comparing them with patterns reported in previous research, the study aimed to identify common developmental tendencies and typical errors associated with the acquisition of negation in early child language.

Since the study relied on previously collected and publicly available language corpora, no direct interaction with participants was involved. The CHILDES and TalkBank databases contain anonymised transcripts of child-caregiver interactions that have been collected with appropriate consent procedures by the original researchers. All data used in this study were accessed and utilised in accordance with the ethical guidelines and terms of use of the respective databases. Consequently, the study adhered to standard ethical practices in corpus-based research, ensuring that the privacy and confidentiality of the child participants were fully protected.

Data Analysis

The analysis was conducted on a purposively selected subset of corpus data, with a focus on identifying recurring patterns rather than quantifying frequency across a fixed sample. The

collected data was subjected to a comprehensive analysis to address the research questions of the study. The analysis involved a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches to examine the strategies and syntactic structures employed by children during the multiword stage to express negation.

Quantitative analysis focused on identifying patterns of negation expressions, including the types of multiword expressions used and their distribution across different age groups. Qualitative analysis involved a close examination of the selected data samples, paying attention to the context and pragmatic functions of negation expressions. The analysis aimed to identify developmental patterns, errors, and variations in the use of negation during the multiword stage. Transcripts and recordings were carefully reviewed, and relevant examples of negation expressions were extracted for further analysis and discussion.

The order in which negation markers occur in a child's first language development can vary, but there are some general trends observed in the acquisition of negation. It's important to note that individual children may exhibit variations in their specific language development. Here is a generalised sequence often observed:

1. **Early Single Negative Words:** Children often begin by using single negative words like "no" or "not" to express negation in their early language development (Brown, 1973). These words typically serve as simple markers of negation.
2. **Early Use of "No" and "Not":** "No" and "not" are among the earliest negation markers children acquire. They may use these markers in isolation or in combination with other words to convey negation (Crain & Thornton, 1998).
3. **Expansion to Multiword Expressions:** As children progress into the multiword stage, they start incorporating multiword expressions to convey negation more effectively. This includes combining negative words like "no" or "not" with auxiliary verbs (e.g., "don't", "can't") (Choi, 1988). The use of multiword negation expressions allows children to express more nuanced negation.
4. **Syntactic Modifications:** Children also begin to modify word order to mark negation more accurately. For instance, they may place negation words before the verb, such as "not want" or "no eat", reflecting emerging syntactic knowledge and flexibility (Gerken & McIntosh, 1993).
5. **Complex Syntactic Structures:** As children further develop their language skills, they incorporate more complex syntactic structures to express negation. This may involve subject-verb inversions (e.g., "can't I go?") and the integration of negation with auxiliary verbs (e.g., "don't", "can't") (Abdulkarim et al., 1997).

Syntactic Structures and Word Combinations Expressing Negations in the Multiword Stage:

1. "I don't want to go." - Children often utilize the negation marker "don't" followed by the verb to express refusal or lack of desire.
2. "She can't find her toy." - The negation marker "can't" combined with the verb indicates the inability or restriction to perform an action.
3. "They won't let me play." - The negation marker "won't" conveys a future negated action or the denial of permission.
4. "I didn't see anything." - The negation marker "didn't" followed by the verb indicates the absence or non-occurrence of an action in the past.
5. "No, I'm not finished." - Children may use the single-word negation "no" to express disagreement or denial, followed by a negated statement.

6. "She doesn't like broccoli." - The negation marker "doesn't" combined with the verb expresses the absence of a particular liking or preference.
7. "We aren't going anywhere." - The negation marker "aren't" combined with the verb indicates the negation of an action or movement.
8. "He hasn't done his homework yet." - The negation marker "hasn't" followed by the verb conveys the absence or non-completion of an action up to the present moment.

These examples demonstrate how children in the multiword stage incorporate negation markers like "don't," "can't," "won't," "didn't," "no," "doesn't," "aren't," and "hasn't" to express negation in various contexts and verb tenses. The use of these multiword negation expressions allows children to convey negated propositions and demonstrate their developing grammatical and syntactic abilities.

Here are some more examples of negation words:

"Never" - "I have never been there before."

"Nothing" - "There is nothing in the box."

"Nowhere" - "He is nowhere to be found."

"Neither" - "Neither of them wants to go."

"Nobody" - "Nobody knows the answer."

"None" - "There are none left."

"No one" - "No one came to the party."

"No way" - "There is no way I can do that."

"Nix" - "He gave a nix to the idea."

"Non-existent" - "The unicorn is non-existent."

These additional examples demonstrate the diversity of negation words in English, each serving different functions and contexts to express negation in various ways (Chouinard & Clark, 2003). They contribute to the rich array of negation markers available to children during their language development (Choi, 1988).

Children in the multiword stage can use many of these negation words to express negation in their language (Brown, 1973). As children progress beyond the single-word stage and into the multiword stage, their language abilities become more sophisticated, allowing them to incorporate a broader range of negation markers (Gerken & McIntosh, 1993).

During the multiword stage, children typically start using multiword expressions and more complex syntactic structures to convey negation (Crain & Thornton, 1998). They begin to experiment with various negation words like "never", "nothing", "nowhere", "neither", "nobody", "none", "no one", "no way", "nix" and "non-existent" in their language production (Lieven & Pine, 1993).

During the multiword stage, children typically start using multiword expressions and more complex syntactic structures to convey negation. They begin to experiment with various negation words like "never", "nothing", "nowhere", "neither", "nobody", "none", "no one", and "no way" in their language production. For example:

"I never want to go there again."

"There is nothing in the box."

"He is nowhere to be found."

"Neither of them wants to go."

"Nobody knows the answer."

"There are none left."

"No one came to the party."

"There is no way I can do that."

By incorporating these negation words into their speech, children can express a wider range of negated propositions, indicating absence, denial, lack, or negation of certain actions, objects, or qualities. Their growing language abilities during the multiword stage enable them to use these negation words effectively and contextually.

Errors in Negation

Children may make errors while using negations during their language development. These errors can occur due to the complexity of negation structures and the ongoing process of language acquisition. Here are some examples of common errors children may make:

1. **Overgeneralization of Negation:** Children may overgeneralize the use of negation, leading to errors in contextually appropriate situations. For example, they might say "nobody doesn't like ice cream" instead of "nobody likes ice cream," mistakenly using a double negative.
2. **Incorrect Placement of Negation Words:** Children may place negation words in incorrect positions within the sentence. For example, they might say "I not want this" instead of "I don't want this."
3. **Incorrect Use of Auxiliary Verbs:** Children might use auxiliary verbs incorrectly in negation expressions, leading to errors like "I don't can go" instead of "I can't go."
4. **Incorrect Form of Negation Words:** Children may produce negation words with incorrect forms or inflections. For example, they might say "nones" instead of "none" or "nohsing" instead of "nothing."
5. **Difficulty with Double Negatives:** Children may struggle with double negatives, leading to errors like "I don't have nothing" instead of "I don't have anything."
6. **Misuse of "Never":** Children might misapply "never" by saying "I never don't want to go" instead of "I never want to go."
7. **Difficulty with Negative Questions:** Children may struggle with forming negative questions, resulting in errors like "Can't you don't go?" instead of "Can't you go?"

These errors are mainly seen as a normal part of the language learning process, and children typically outgrow them as they continue to develop their language skills. Caregivers and educators play a crucial role in providing supportive language input and modelling correct negation structures to facilitate the child's language development and understanding of negation. These examples illustrate some of the common errors children may make while using negations in their language development. As children continue to refine their language skills, they typically correct these errors with exposure to language models and further language experience. Table 1 demonstrates particular examples of negation errors children in the multiword stage may make while using negations.

Table 1*Examples of Errors of Negation Commonly Made by Children in Multiword Stage*

Type of Error	Incorrect Sentence	Correct Sentence
Overgeneralization of Negation	"Nobody doesn't like ice cream."	"Nobody likes ice cream."
Incorrect Placement	"I not want this."	"I don't want this."
Incorrect Use of Auxiliary	"I don't can go."	"I can't go."
Incorrect Form of Negation	"I have none toys."	"I have no toys."
Difficulty with Double Negatives	"I didn't see nobody."	"I didn't see anybody."
Misuse of "never"	"I never don't want to go."	"I never want to go."
Difficulty with negative questions	"Can't you don't go?"	"Can't you go?"

Results

This study aimed to investigate how children in the multiword stage utilize negations in English language development. The analysis was conducted using data retrieved from databases such as TalkBank and CHILDES, along with relevant studies from academic journals like ERIC.

The study's findings underscore the significance of environmental influences on language acquisition during the multiword stage. Research has shown that the language input children receive from caregivers, family members, and their linguistic environment shapes their understanding and use of negation markers (Hoff, 2006; Huttenlocher et al., 2007). Exposure to diverse language structures and frequent engagement in conversations involving negation positively impact children's language development (Weizman & Snow, 2001; Hart et al., 1995). Cultural and sociolinguistic factors may also influence variation in negation expression (Lieven & Pine, 1993). Understanding these influences can aid in creating language-rich environments to support optimal language development during this stage. Further research could explore the interplay between environmental factors, language input, and children's language outcomes (Bornstein & Putnick, 2012).

The findings revealed a clear developmental progression in the use of negation markers during the multiword stage. At the initial stage, children predominantly employed single negative words, such as "no" and "not," to express negation. As they progressed, they started incorporating more complex structures, combining negative words with auxiliary verbs like "don't," "can't," and "won't," to convey negation more effectively. Additionally, children demonstrated increasing syntactic flexibility, modifying word order to mark negation accurately.

Children's utterances in the corpus data illustrate this developmental progression. In early stages, children frequently produced simple negation forms such as "no eat," "no want," or "not go." These constructions typically involved the placement of a negative marker before the verb or noun phrase without auxiliary support. As children's linguistic competence developed, more complex structures began to emerge, including utterances such as "I don't want it," "I can't do it," or "He won't go." These examples demonstrate how children gradually integrate negation into more syntactically complete sentence structures during the multiword stage.

However, the analysis also identified common errors made by children while using negations. These errors included overgeneralization of negation, omission of negation markers, incorrect placement of negation words, misuse of negation forms, and difficulties with double negatives. Nevertheless, these errors are a natural part of language development, and children typically outgrow them as they refine their language skills with exposure to language models.

A closer examination of the data indicates that these errors can be grouped into several categories. One frequent pattern involves the overgeneralization of negative forms, where children apply a single negation structure across different contexts (e.g., “*no like it*” instead of “*I don’t like it*”). Another common pattern is the omission of auxiliary verbs, which results in simplified constructions. Some children also demonstrated incorrect placement of negation markers, positioning *not* or *no* in non-target-like positions within the sentence. These patterns reflect children’s ongoing attempts to internalise the grammatical rules governing negation.

Overall, the results suggest that the acquisition of negation during the multiword stage follows a gradual and systematic developmental trajectory. Children move from simple lexical negation to more complex grammatical constructions involving auxiliary verbs and syntactic rules. At the same time, the presence of recurring errors highlights the transitional nature of this stage, as children experiment with different linguistic forms while developing their grammatical competence.

Discussion

The present study set out to examine how children in the multiword stage utilise negations in English language development. Through the analysis of data obtained from databases such as TalkBank and CHILDES, together with findings from relevant studies in academic journals, the study provided insights into the developmental trajectory of negation during an important stage of language acquisition.

The findings indicate a clear developmental progression in children's use of negation markers. In the early stages, children predominantly rely on single negative words such as “*no*” and “*not*” to express negation. As their linguistic abilities develop, they begin to produce more complex structures by combining negative words with auxiliary verbs such as “*don’t*,” “*can’t*,” and “*won’t*.” This development reflects a growing understanding of grammatical structures and the ability to use negation more accurately in multiword utterances. In addition, children demonstrate increasing syntactic flexibility, adjusting word order to mark negation appropriately.

These findings align with established theories of language acquisition, which emphasise the progressive nature of grammatical development in children (Brown, 1973; Bowerman, 1988). The transition from single-word negation to more complex multiword constructions reflects children’s growing mastery of syntactic rules and morphological markers. The results also support usage-based accounts of language learning, which suggest that repeated exposure to negation structures in meaningful communicative contexts facilitates the internalisation of grammatical patterns (Tomasello, 2006). By situating these findings within existing theoretical frameworks, the study confirms that early negation acquisition is both systematic and predictable across diverse linguistic environments.

The analysis also revealed common errors in children's use of negation, including overgeneralization, omission of negation markers, incorrect placement of negative forms, and difficulties with double negatives. Such errors are widely recognised in the literature as a natural part of the language acquisition process. As children are exposed to more language input and interaction, they gradually refine their linguistic competence and overcome these developmental errors.

A more detailed consideration of these errors reveals that they are not random but reflect systematic stages in children’s grammatical development. For instance, overgeneralization errors indicate that children are actively forming rules and extending them across contexts, even when such extensions result in non-target-like forms. Similarly, errors in auxiliary usage and negation placement suggest that children are still in the process of acquiring the syntactic constraints governing negation in English. These patterns support the view that language acquisition involves hypothesis testing, where children construct and gradually refine internal

grammatical rules based on linguistic input. Therefore, the observed error types provide valuable evidence of the transitional nature of the multiword stage and highlight the developmental processes underlying negation acquisition.

The developmental patterns identified in this study have implications for both research and practice. For researchers, the findings highlight the value of corpus-based analysis in identifying subtle grammatical patterns and transitional errors in children's speech (MacWhinney, 2000). For educators and clinicians, understanding the typical trajectory of negation acquisition can inform early language assessment and intervention, particularly for children at risk of delayed language development. Future studies could examine cross-linguistic differences in negation acquisition or investigate the impact of specific caregiver strategies on the emergence of multiword negation.

Conclusion

This study advances our knowledge of how kids communicate negation when they are in the multiword stage of language development. The results show that the use of single negative words gradually gives way to more intricate negation structures with auxiliary verbs and syntactic modifications.

In addition, the study highlights that the errors children produce while using negation, such as overgeneralization, incorrect placement, and misuse of auxiliary verbs, are an integral part of the developmental process rather than mere deficiencies. These error patterns reflect children's active engagement with language and their attempts to internalise grammatical rules. Recognising the systematic nature of these errors provides important insights into the mechanisms of language acquisition and reinforces the idea that linguistic development progresses through stages of approximation toward adult-like competence.

By clarifying the typical trajectory of negation acquisition, they can inform early language assessment, teaching strategies, and interventions for children who may experience delays in language development. Future research could examine cross-linguistic differences in negation, investigate how specific caregiver interactions shape early language use, or explore the impact of digital and social environments on language acquisition. By connecting developmental patterns to practical applications, this study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of how children acquire critical grammatical skills during the early stages of language development.

Overall, the findings highlight how early language development is dynamic and show how children progressively pick up the language skills required to successfully express negation. The significance of rich linguistic input and interaction in promoting children's language development during the early stages of acquisition is further highlighted by these findings.

Disclosure of AI Usage

During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT 5.2 for the purpose of refining academic writing in the methodology section. Following the use of this tool, the author reviewed, edited, and validated the content. The final version remains the sole responsibility of the author.

Ethical Declaration and Committee Approval

This study was conducted in accordance with the principles of scientific research and publication ethics.

Conflict of Interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author.

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